

Supplementary Figure 8. Multipotency of PICs *in vivo*. (A) Fluorescent microscope images of GFP-transduced C9 PICs. Scale =200 μ m. (B) Flow cytometric analysis of GFP expression in transduced C9 PICs (green histogram), compared to mock transduced cells (grey histogram) (C) Teratomas viewed on the kidney of mice after 4 weeks. No teratomas evident in SHAM, (n=2) or PIC-treated animals (n=3). Teratoma formation observed in PIC/ESC, (n=3) and ESC-treated, (n=2) animals. (D) Variety of cell morphologies seen in teratomas; visualised by haematoxylin and eosin staining. Scale =200 μ m (top left) and 20 μ m all other images. (E-F) GFP was detected in teratomas generated by GFP^{pos} PIC/ESC-treated mice only and not in ESC-treated mice, shown by DAB staining (E) and immunofluorescence staining (F). Scale =100 μ m.